

Application of Modern Technologies in Teaching Business Studies Subjects in Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

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Abstract

The study examined Application of Modern Technologies in teaching Business Studies in secondary schools in Rivers State. The research adopted a descriptive survey design. Three objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses were posed to guide the study. The population for the study was 249 all Business Studies Subjects teachers in Urban and Rural areas of Rivers State. No sampling technique was used since the population was manageable. The Instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled "Modern Technologies Utilization in Teaching Business Studies Subjects in secondary schools" (MTUTBSSSS). The reliability of the research instrument was obtained using Cronbach alpha method and a reliability coefficient of 0.75 was established. 247 copies of the questionnaire were retrieved and analyzed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions and t-test for the hypothesis at .05 level of significance. The results obtained indicated that Modern Technologies Utilization in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State is high extent for Urban and low extent for Rural areas. Thus, the study recommended that Business Studies programme managers should insist in the application of Modern Technologies Utilization and practical steps should be taking to encourage its usage in teaching the students for them to gain the requisite knowledge of operating these packages/applications in the world of business.

Keywords: Modern, Technologies, Application, Teaching and Business Studies

Introduction

All over the world, technological advancement has continued to change the way people perform tasks and solve their daily problems. This has affected the operational processes in various sectors of the economy and the way people teach and learn. Teaching is an attempt to assist people to acquire some skills, attitudes, knowledge or ideas. Teaching is also an interaction between teachers and students under the auspices and responsibilities of the teacher in order to bring about the expected change in the students` behavior. Teaching profession is an act of relating information to the learner or assisting the learner on how to do something. It involves the process of assisting the learner to gain useful skills, attitudes, knowledge, ideas; values in an arranged or unarranged environment that will assist the learner become an acceptable person to the society, independent in life with relatively permanent change (Ukata & Silas – Dikibo, 2019). The e-learning coach (2018) argued that the relatively permanent change in a person`s knowledge or behaviour due is to experience which require Modern Technologies in modern day teaching. The definition has three components: 1. the duration of the change is long-term rather than short-term; 2. the locus of the change is the contents and structure of knowledge in memory or the behaviour of the learner;

3. the cause of the change in the learner's experience in the environment which require teaching with new technologies.

Modern Technology refers to the production and utilization of technological tools and their interaction with society, the environment, and various domains of human activity. It encompasses the transformation of scientific knowledge into products, processes, services, and organizational structures. According to Amali (2014), Modern Technology refers to visual, audio and audio-visual category, which helps to make abstract concepts and ideas concrete in the teaching and learning process. They include overhead projectors, films, interactive white board, digital camera, television, photocopier, printer and laptop computers.

Monsuru (2015), stated that teaching in this modern period is increasingly becoming more complex and technological to be teaching with traditional tools (such as chalkboard, textbooks, chart, pictures, and map among others). Monsuru further stated that, developments in Modern Technology have made available a wide range of instructional materials to supplement teachers' effort in teaching-learning process. Nwagwu and Azih (2016) posited that vocational education which is the vehicle through which business subjects hope to accomplish their objectives is susceptible to changes with innovations in technologies especially those used in modern offices and schools. This is why business subjects teachers are expected to utilize appropriate Modern Technologies in teaching so that students can have opportunity to see, touch and manipulate them. Business Studies can therefore be viewed as a subject thought in junior secondary school that in stils in the learner, skills and aptitude that is required to succeed in the world of business. Thus, it is required that learners be given the best of knowledge in terms of theories and practical's in the Business Studies subject. Teaching and learning of Business Studies should encompass Modern Technological facilities, since one vital need in the present business environment is the ability to use computer applications for different purposes (Edeh, 2017). Ugwu (2016) revealed that the high rate of poor performance of students in business subjects in both internal and external examinations could be attributed to inadequate Modern Technologies utilization by teachers. Chukwuka (2017), there are various factors responsible for the poor performance of students in Business Studies subject one of which is low utilization of Modern Technologies by Business Studies subject teachers in the teaching process.

Modern Technologies application by Business Studies subject teachers could be influenced by school location, gender and years of teaching experience. It could be that secondary schools in urban areas have more Modern Technologies Utilization than those in rural areas which could make Business Studies subject teachers in urban areas to utilize it in teaching more than their rural counterparts. However, Usman (2016) revealed no significant difference between urban and rural teachers' responses regarding the utilization of Modern Technologies Utilization in teaching. Similarly, male teachers could utilize Modern Technologies in teaching more than their female counterparts. In relation to this, Ngeru (2015) found out that a significant difference existed between male and female teachers on the extent of application of Modern Technologies for teaching. Furthermore, years of experience could influence Business Studies subject teachers' responses on the utilization of Modern Technologies. Experienced Business Studies subject teachers (above 5 years) could differ significantly with their inexperienced counterparts (0 – 5 years) on level of utilization of Modern Technologies for Teaching and Learning delivery. Amuzu (2018) revealed that years of experience of teachers influence their utilization of Modern Technologies in teaching. It is against this background that this study assessed the Modern Technologies utilization in teaching Business Studies Subjects in secondary School in Rivers State.

Basargekar and Singhavi (2017) opined those inadequate ICT resources; low teacher confidence; lack of motivation; lack of competence; and teachers' attitude toward the utilization of modern technologies for effective teaching and learning are major barriers experienced by school teachers in facilitating successful integration of Modern Technology for teaching purposes, especially in a developing country like Nigeria. This means that most teachers are confronted with pedagogical experiences while also having insufficient expertise in how to apply and use digital technology effectively in their professional activities. The authors emphasized that the success or failure of Modern Technology deployment is determined by teachers' perceptions of their ability to use technology in the classroom. Instructors' perceptions of their ability are influenced by both non-manipulative (demographic features of the teachers) and manipulative (language of delivery, school board, and training facilities) teacher factors. Teachers' training should focus on pedagogical issues, if they are to be convinced of the value of employing Modern Technology in their work. Individuals in Nigeria today may not use Modern Technology services for a variety of reasons, including a lack of interest, illiteracy, lack of awareness, high service rates, and poor service quality. Operational terms include:

(i) Accessibility can be defined as the ability to use a system or entity's capabilities and potential benefits. It is important to ensure that services and information are accessible to a wide range of people when it comes to Modern Technology accessibility.

(ii) Usability is a fundamental criterion for assessing technological developments; it ensures the quality of e-learning devices and places users and their demands at the forefront of technological development. It also assures that a product can be used by specific users to achieve specific goals in a specific context with effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction.

(iii) Readiness is a metric for assessing the quality of Modern Technology infrastructure at the national level or within major businesses. It can assess a consumer's, a business's, or a government's ability to gain from Modern Technology.

(iv) Monitoring is a technique for ensuring and improving the efficacy and efficiency of a program's implementation. The use of Modern Technologies to assist, enhance, and optimize the transmission of information is referred to as Modern Technology in education.

The use of Modern Technologies in educational practice is widely regarded to empower both teachers and students, encourage change, and stimulate the development of 21st-century skills. Modern Technologies can use shift teaching and learning processes from a teacher-centered to a student-centered approach. Related studies on technology integration in Nigerian education developments have opened up possibilities for bettering teaching and learning, particularly in terms of resource access. For example, the Internet provides learning venues and capacities for bridging the gap between students and teachers. As a result, technological advancements have led to numerous forms of technology integration in education, such as mobile learning, online learning, and blended learning. Educational activities can now be conducted via electronic mail, chats, web-based conferencing, messaging platforms, and web pages for sharing information resources as a result of these technological advancements (Utulu & Alonge, 2012). As a result of these educational activities, interactive and collaborative learning is facilitated, and assessment is improved during the teaching-learning process. Support, accessibility, infrastructure, learning tools, and cognitive are five categories of characteristics that influence the usage of Modern Technology in Nigerian secondary schools, according to a factor analysis study (Ogundile, 2019). Unfortunately, according to a recent assessment, Modern Technology readiness in Rivers State is still quite poor, with most governments experiencing significant delays in the acquisition of

facilities due to a lack of finances. Taiwo and Ade-Ajayi (2015) revealed that teachers' educational attainment can have great influence on perceived factors affecting effective teaching and learning. Taiwo and Ade-Ajayi (2015) further advanced that educational attainment of teachers can have influence on their understanding of the subject matter, selection of tools, use of appropriate instructional strategies and classroom management skills applied in teaching. Top Education Degrees (2020) averred that, institution ownership play major roles in Teachers' level of Modern Technologies application for developing employability skills among students. This is because federal institutions may provide better salary packages, better teaching environments, aids, laboratories, motivation, worker-friendly policies, compensation and staff development programme than state institutions. So, they are variables of interest.

The justification for this topic "Application of Modern Technologies in Teaching Business Studies Subjects in Secondary Schools in Rivers State" was because, although there are related literature to this study, there is no exact study like this in contents and scope with the same moderated factors. Therefore, this investigation is exceptional among others and a new path in the body of knowledge.

Statement of the Problem

The Modern day Technologies of teaching Business Studies Subjects in Secondary Schools requires Teachers with a very high level of application of Modern Technologies to enable Students acquire the needed skills to as to gainfully employed and reduced unemployment rates. Unfortunately, most Business Studies Teachers have not been able to utilize Modern Technologies in teaching Business Studies students which have contributed to high rate of employability skills and unemployment for lack of skills and competencies. No wonder Nwaukwa (2015) lamented that majority of business teachers lacked computer skills required to integrate Modern Technologies for successful instructional delivery as required for implementing ICT-based curriculum. Also, Fadare (2014) identified problems and bewailed that Business Teachers in secondary schools are not adequately utilizing computer for teaching Business Studies subject due to their lack Modern Technology skills and modern instructional competencies this may be because cooperative instructional teaching were not adopted.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study was to examine the Application of Modern Technologies Utilization in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the study examined:

1. The availability of Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies in secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. The accessibility of Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies in secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. The utilization of Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. To what extent are Modern Technologies tools available in teaching Business Studies in secondary schools in Rivers State?

2. To what extent are Modern Technologies tools accessible in teaching Business Studies in secondary schools in Rivers State?
3. To what extent are Business Studies teachers utilizing Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies in secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business Studies teachers in urban and rural areas on the availability of Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies in secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business Studies teachers in urban and rural areas on the accessibility of Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies in secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business Studies teachers in urban and rural areas on the extent they utilize Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Methods

The design adopted for this study was the descriptive survey. The population of the study comprised 249 Business Studies subject's teachers in the 253 public secondary schools in Rivers State where business studies subjects are taught both in rural and urban secondary schools. There was no sampling since the population was not too large. The instrument for data collection for the study was a structured questionnaire titled "Modern Technologies Utilization in Teaching Business Studies Subjects in secondary schools (MTUTBSSSS)". The questionnaire was structured on a four-point scale, with response categories as Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) with assigned weighted values of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The face validity of the instrument was established using the opinions of experts in Business Education and Measurement and Evaluation from the Faculty Education Rivers State University. The reliability of the instrument was established using trial test and data collected were analyzed using Cronbach alpha which yielded coefficient value of 0.75. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. A hypothesis was rejected where the p-value was less than the level of significance value. Otherwise, the hypothesis was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent are Modern Technologies tools available in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean responses on the extent Modern Technologies tools are available in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State.

S/N	Items	Urban Teachers (n=136)			Rural Teachers (n=111)		
		Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Projectors are available for the use of teaching and learning of business studies subjects in my school.	2.64	1.07	High	1.53	0.86	Low
2	Laptop computers are available for the use of teaching and learning of business studies subjects in my school.	2.76	0.98	High	1.68	0.94	Low
3	Instructive white board are available for the use of teaching and learning of business studies subjects in my school.	2.76	1.07	High	2.01	1.12	Low
4	Digital camera are available for the use of teaching and learning of business studies subjects in my school.	2.54	1.03	High	1.58	0.90	Low
5	Printer and photocopier are available for the use of teaching and learning of business studies subjects in my school.	2.76	0.98	High	1.68	0.94	Low
Grand mean		2.69	0.91	High	1.70	0.74	Low

The result in the table shows the mean responses on the extent to which modern technology tools are available for teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State. The grand mean scores for urban and rural teachers were 2.69 and 1.70, respectively, indicating a high availability of modern technology tools in urban schools and low availability in rural schools. The grand mean scores indicate a clear disparity in the availability of modern technology tools between urban and rural schools. Urban teachers reported high availability across all items, with mean scores above 2.50, highlighting that projectors, laptop computers, instructive whiteboards, digital cameras, and printers/photocopiers are generally accessible for teaching Business Studies subjects. The low standard deviations further emphasize the consistency of responses among urban teachers. In contrast, rural teachers reported low availability of these tools, with mean scores below 2.50 for all items. This suggests that rural schools lack essential modern technology tools necessary for effective teaching and learning of Business Studies subjects. The relatively low standard deviations among rural teachers' responses indicate a consistent perception of insufficient technological resources across rural schools.

Research Question 2: To what extent are Modern Technologies tools accessible in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean responses on the extent Modern Technologies tools are accessible in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State.

S/N	Items	Urban Teachers (n=136)			Rural Teachers (n=111)		
		Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark
6	Projectors are accessible for the use of teaching and learning of business studies subjects in my school.	2.64	1.05	High	2.22	1.05	Low
7	Laptop computer are accessible for the use of teaching and learning of business studies subjects in my school.	2.90	0.98	High	2.53	1.12	High
8	Instructive white board are accessible for the use of teaching and learning of business studies subjects in my school.	2.86	1.02	High	2.50	1.14	High
9	Digital camera are accessible for the use of teaching and learning of business studies subjects in my school.	2.54	1.02	High	2.08	1.05	Low
10	Printer and photocopier are accessible for the use of teaching and learning of business studies subjects in my school.	2.60	1.04	High	2.18	1.07	Low
Grand mean		2.71	0.92	High	2.30	0.98	Low

The result in the table shows the mean responses on the extent to which modern technology tools are accessible for teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State. The grand mean scores for urban and rural teachers were 2.71 and 2.30, respectively, indicating high accessibility of modern technology tools in urban schools and low accessibility in rural schools. The grand mean scores suggest a disparity in the accessibility of modern technology tools between urban and rural schools. Urban teachers reported high accessibility across all items, with mean scores above 2.50, indicating that projectors, laptop computers, instructive whiteboards, digital cameras, and printers/photocopiers are generally accessible for teaching Business Studies subjects. The low standard deviations among urban teachers' responses indicate consistency in the perception of accessibility. In contrast, rural teachers reported lower accessibility of these tools, with mean scores above 2.50 for only two items (laptop computers and instructive whiteboards), while the rest were below 2.50, indicating low accessibility. The relatively higher standard deviations among rural teachers' responses suggest variability in the availability of these tools across different rural schools.

Research Question 3: To what extent are Business Studies teachers utilizing Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean responses on the extent Business Studies teachers utilize Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State.

S/N	Items	Urban Teachers (n=136)			Rural Teachers (n=111)		
		Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark
11	I utilize projectors for the use of teaching and learning in my school.	2.60	1.04	High	1.66	0.91	Low
12	I utilize laptop computer for the use of teaching and learning in my school.	2.52	1.04	High	2.08	1.13	Low
13	I utilize instructive white board for the use of teaching and learning in my school.	2.51	1.00	High	1.92	1.13	Low
14	I utilize digital camera for the use of teaching and learning in my school.	2.61	1.01	High	1.72	0.90	Low
15	I utilize printer and photocopier for the use of teaching and learning in my school.	2.52	1.04	High	2.08	1.13	Low
Grand mean		2.55	0.93	High	1.89	0.86	Low

The result in the table shows the mean responses on the extent to which Business Studies teachers utilize modern technology tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State. The grand mean scores for urban and rural teachers were 2.55 and 1.89, respectively, indicating high utilization of modern technology tools in urban schools and low utilization in rural schools. The grand mean scores suggest a disparity in the utilization of modern technology tools between urban and rural schools. Urban teachers reported high utilization across all items, with mean scores above 2.50, indicating that projectors, laptop computers, instructive whiteboards, digital cameras, and printers/photocopiers are generally utilized for teaching Business Studies subjects. The relatively low standard deviations among urban teachers' responses indicate consistency in the utilization of these tools. In contrast, rural teachers reported lower utilization of these tools, with mean scores below 2.50 for all items, indicating low utilization. The higher standard deviations among rural teachers' responses suggest variability in the utilization of these tools across different rural schools.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business Studies teachers in urban and rural areas on the availability of Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of Independent Sample t-test on the difference in the mean responses of Business Studies teachers in urban and rural areas on the availability of Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Location	N	Mean	SD	SDE	t	df	p-value	Decision
Urban Teachers	136	2.69	0.91	0.08	9.327	245	.000	Rejected Ho ₁
Rural Teachers	111	1.70	0.74	0.07				

The result from Table 4 presents the summary of an independent sample t-test on the difference in the mean responses of Business Studies teachers in urban and rural areas on the availability of modern technology tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State. The analysis yielded a p-value of .000, which is lower than the predetermined significance level of 0.05. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis (Ho₁) and conclude that there is a significant difference in the mean responses of Business Studies teachers in urban and rural areas regarding the availability of modern technology tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business Studies teachers in urban and rural areas on the accessibility of Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 5: Summary of Independent Sample t-test on the difference in the mean responses of Business Studies teachers in urban and rural areas on the accessibility of Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Location	N	Mean	SD	SDE	t	df	p-value	Decision
Urban Teachers	136	2.71	0.92	0.08	3.338	245	.001	Rejected Ho ₂
Rural Teachers	111	2.30	0.98	0.09				

The result from Table 5 presents the summary of an independent sample t-test on the difference in the mean responses of Business Studies teachers in urban and rural areas on the accessibility of modern technology tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State. The analysis yielded a p-value of .001, which is lower than the predetermined significance level of 0.05. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis (Ho₂) and conclude that there is a significant difference in the mean responses of Business Studies teachers in urban and rural areas regarding the accessibility of modern technology tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business Studies teachers in urban and rural areas on the extent they utilize Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 6: Summary of Independent Sample t-test on the difference in the mean responses of Business Studies teachers in urban and rural areas on the extent they utilize Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Location	N	Mean	SD	SDE	t	df	p-value	Decision
Urban Teachers	136	2.55	0.93	0.08				
					5.034	208	.000	Rejected Ho ₃
Rural Teachers	74	1.89	0.86	0.10				

The result from Table 6 presents the summary of an independent sample t-test on the difference in the mean responses of Business Studies teachers in urban and rural areas on the extent they utilize modern technology tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State. The analysis yielded a p-value of .000, which is lower than the predetermined significance level of 0.05. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis (Ho₃) and conclude that there is a significant difference in the mean responses of Business Studies teachers in urban and rural areas regarding the extent they utilize modern technology tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Discussion of the Findings

The discussion in this study was done according to the findings of the study.

The availability of Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State.

The findings from the first research question revealed that the availability of Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State was high extend for Urban teachers and low extent to Rural teachers. This findings was in agreement with Kabiru and Sakiyo (2013), is a contributing factors impeding the use of Modern Technologies for instructional reasons. The authors also discovered that teachers lacked time to learn new skills, had a significant number of students enrolled in their classes, and had an insufficient quantity of computers available in the classroom for student use. Secondary school instructors in Nigeria. Based on the findings the researcher is suggesting that Government should provide or make Modern Technologies available to both Urban and Rural Schools to enhance the teaching of Business Studies Subject.

The accessibility of Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State.

The findings from the second research question revealed that the accessibility of Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State was high extend for Urban teachers and low extent to Rural teachers. This findings was in agreement with Ogundile (2019), As a result of these educational activities, interactive and collaborative learning is facilitated, and assessment is improved during the teaching-learning process. Support, accessibility, infrastructure, learning tools, and cognitive are five categories of characteristics that influence the usage of Modern Technology in Nigerian secondary schools, according to a factor analysis study. Unfortunately, according to a recent assessment, Modern Technology readiness in Rivers State is still quite poor, with most governments experiencing significant delays in the acquisition of facilities due to a lack of finances. Based on the findings the researcher is suggesting

that Government should provide Modern Technologies to both Urban and Rural Schools, so that the teachers can be able to access them in teaching of Business Studies Subject.

The utilization of Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State.

The findings from the second research question revealed that the Utilization of Modern Technologies tools in teaching Business Studies subjects in secondary schools in Rivers State was high extend for Urban teachers and low extent to Rural teachers. This finding was in agreement with Uwaifo in Ugwu (2016), proper utilization of Modern Technologies serves a useful purpose in promoting understanding to concepts and principles. In relation to that Ugwu posited that proper utilization of relevant equipment, materials tools or instructional facilities in teaching business subjects facilitates learning and enhances student's achievement. Modern Technologies Utilization by Business Subjects Teachers will improve more the standard of teaching and learning of Business Subjects in secondary schools. It is therefore important that the Business Subjects teachers should be conversant with different Modern Technologies effectively utilize them while teaching.

Conclusion

The study revealed that Modern Technologies Utilization is very important in the teaching and learning of Business Studies Subject in Secondary Schools in Rivers State. However, it is yet to be fully available, access and utilized in teaching of Business Studies Subject.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Business Studies programme managers should insist in the application of Modern Technologies Utilization and practical steps should be taking to encourage its usage in teaching the students for them to gain the requisite knowledge of operating these packages/applications in the world of business.
2. Government and other stakeholders should endeavor to make available and accessible the necessary Modern Technologies facilities (software, hardware and internet); this will automatically encourage its utilization in teaching Business Studies Subjects.

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